

Kinetics of Oxidation of Maltose and Lactose by Cerium(IV) in Sulphuric Acid Solution

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The kinetic study of Ce^{IV} oxidation of maltose and lactose in aqueous sulphuric acid medium shows first order kinetics with respect to both Ce^{IV} as well as substrate. The reaction rate decreases on increasing the concentration of hydrogen ion. The sulphate ion shows retarding effect on reaction rate. The values of activation energy have been calculated and a suitable mechanism conforming to the kinetic data is proposed.

A survey of literature has shown that kinetics of oxidation of maltose and lactose by Ce^{IV} have not been studied. This paper deals with the kinetic study of Ce^{IV} oxidation of maltose and lactose in aqueous sulphuric acid medium.

Experimental

All the materials used were of analytical reagent grade.

A standard stock solution of sodium thiosulphate was prepared¹. Ceric ammonium sulphate solution prepared in 2N H₂SO₄ solution was standardised iodometrically. The kinetics were followed by removing aliquots (5 ml) from the reaction mixture at different intervals and the reaction was arrested by adding aqueous 5% KI solution (10 ml). The liberated iodine which is equivalent to the concentration of the unreacted cerium(IV), was determined by titration with standard sodium thiosulphate.

The reaction was found to be first order in both cerium(IV) and the either substrate. Increase of H₂SO₄ concentration decreases in the reaction rate (Table 1).

Table 2 includes the kinetic data obtained at different temperatures and various concentrations of HSO₄⁻. Decreasing trend in the values of k₁ at higher values of ionic strength of the medium is also obvious from the data. The values of energy of activation (ΔE) in the oxidation of maltose and lactose were found to be 23 ± 0.2 and 26 ± 0.1 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively.

A perusal of literature regarding Ce^{IV} oxidation in sulphuric acid shows the complex formation of Ce^{IV} with sulphate ions. Earlier workers described various species² of Ce^{IV} in sulphuric acid solution. The kinetic results recorded in Tables 1 and 2 are in good agreement with the following mechanism.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON REACTION VELOCITY CONSTANT AT 45° (MALTOSE) AND 40° (LACTOSE)

Ionic strength (μ) = 1.62					
[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ³ M	[Substrate] × 10 ³ M	[H ₂ SO ₄] × 10 M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₂ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ min ⁻¹	
In oxidation of maltose					
3.90	1.00	5.00	4.40	—	
5.00	1.00	5.00	4.80	—	
6.00	1.00	5.00	5.05	—	
8.00	1.00	5.00	5.02	—	
10.00	1.00	5.00	4.86	—	
2.50	0.80	5.00	3.92	4.15	
2.50	1.00	5.00	5.52	5.52	
2.50	1.25	5.00	6.64	5.31	
2.50	1.40	5.00	7.20	5.14	
2.50	1.66	5.00	8.00	4.81	
2.50	2.00	5.00	11.00	5.50	
2.37 ^a	1.25	2.50	9.08	—	
2.37 ^a	1.25	4.50	7.80	—	
2.37 ^a	1.25	6.50	4.60	—	
2.37 ^a	1.25	8.50	4.14	—	
2.37 ^a	1.25	10.50	3.84	—	
2.37 ^a	1.25	12.50	3.42	—	
In oxidation of lactose					
1.00	2.50	5.00	3.00	—	
1.25	2.50	5.00	3.20	—	
1.67	2.50	5.00	3.59	—	
2.50	2.50	5.00	3.68	—	
5.00	2.50	5.00	3.60	—	
10.00	2.50	5.00	3.51	—	
1.57	0.50	5.00	1.15	2.99	
1.57	0.75	5.00	1.58	2.04	
1.57	1.00	5.00	2.16	2.16	
1.57	2.50	5.00	5.29	2.12	
1.57	3.50	5.00	7.26	2.08	
1.57	5.00	5.00	10.19	2.04	
1.60 ^b	2.50	2.50	8.68	—	
1.60 ^b	2.50	5.00	5.18	—	
1.60 ^b	2.50	9.00	3.44	—	
1.60 ^b	2.50	13.00	2.88	—	
1.60 ^b	2.50	17.00	2.19	—	
1.60 ^b	2.50	25.00	1.63	—	

Ionic strength : ^a3.80, ^b7.65.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF CONCENTRATION OF HSO₄⁻, IONIC STRENGTH (μ) AND TEMPERATURE ON REACTION VELOCITY

Temp. °C	[HSO ₄ ⁻] M	Ionic strength (μ)	k × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
In oxidation of maltose*			
35	—	1.545	2.37
40	—	1.545	4.30
45	—	1.545	7.04
50	—	1.545	11.56
45	0.50	3.545	2.08
45	0.75	3.545	1.76
45	1.00	3.545	1.52
45	2.00	3.545	0.84
45	—	1.545	6.98
45	—	1.619	6.04
45	—	1.694	5.36
45	—	1.769	4.81
45	—	1.919	3.85
In oxidation of lactose**			
35	—	1.528	3.00
40	—	1.528	5.43
45	—	1.528	8.84
50	—	1.528	15.43
40	0.50	3.528	2.12
40	0.75	3.528	1.77
40	1.00	3.528	1.38
40	2.00	3.528	0.93
40	—	1.605	2.86
40	—	1.680	2.32
40	—	1.755	2.04
40	—	1.830	1.92
40	—	1.905	1.60

* [Ce^{IV}] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ M, [Maltose] = 1.25 × 10⁻² M,
[H₂SO₄] = 0.5 M.** [Ce^{IV}] = 1.57 × 10⁻³ M, [Lactose] = 2.50 × 10⁻² M,
[H₂SO₄] = 0.5 M.

where M stands for maltose and lactose, and

The rate of reaction may be expressed in terms of loss of concentration of Ce^{IV}. Hence the rate is expressed as equation (1).

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k_2[X] \quad (1)$$

The mechanism leads to the rate law (2),

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2}{(k_{-1} + k_2)} [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{M}] \quad (2)$$

In cerium(IV) oxidations, it has been proposed that the inhibitory action is due to HSO₄⁻ ion³. The inhibitory action⁴ of HSO₄⁻ ion is explained as due to conversion of the reactive form of cerium(IV), Ce(SO₄)₂ to the unreactive species Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻ according to the equilibrium (a),

Similarly, with the increase of sulphuric acid concentration the reaction velocity would also decrease.

Various experiments with different ratios of [Ce(IV)] and [Maltose] or [Lactose] were performed. Estimation of excess Ce^{IV} indicates that 24 moles of Ce^{IV} were required to oxidise each mole of maltose or lactose. The oxidation product in each case was found to be formic acid, which was identified by tlc.

References

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